

Do Pennsylvania Food Safety Inspections Ensure our Safety? The Stats Say No.

By Blake Pierpoint

Imagine cutting the grass once a year. The lawn would look good for a week, but gradually it would grow unkempt. Currently, all food businesses and dairy product manufacturers in the state of Pennsylvania must undergo state-mandated safety inspections. In the eyes of the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture, safety inspections every 12 months is sufficient in ensuring the health of the public. Simply put, the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture is fine with cutting the grass once a year. With the growing concerns for food safety and research becoming more worrying, the need for reform is greater now than ever before. This unkempt lawn can potentially lead to the rapid transmission of infectious gastrointestinal diseases. To lower the risks of enteric outbreaks and ensure statewide health, the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture should implement stricter safety inspection regulations.

You walk into your favorite local restaurant eager to refresh your palate with a variety of new culinary choices. The smell of a new experience intrigues you, and as you are seated the new manager of the establishment walks up and greets you with a warm and welcoming smile. “Enjoy” he states with a reassuring bow. You patiently await your food, and as you look around you notice something different; the food doesn’t look as fresh; the salads don’t seem to have the cleanest lettuce; the steak has a peculiar color. That night you go home disappointed and the following morning you wake in a cold sweat with a pounding headache, a fever of 102 degrees, and a sharp abdominal pain. Almost out of thin air you develop a gastrointestinal infection that will leave you bed ridden for weeks, maybe even requiring prolonged hospital care.

Such is the case for 313 Pennsylvanians, who in 2013, contracted Salmonellosis (Cohrs 3). Salmonellosis, more commonly known as Salmonella poisoning, is a foodborne illness

caused by a vicious gastrointestinal bacterium. Sufferers experience excruciating cramps, severe dehydration, vomiting and fatigue. In fact, CDC reports that an estimated 380 people died of Salmonella poisoning in 2016 alone. Fecal contamination is the most common form of contamination, which usually occurs during the processing and handling of food (Cohrs 6).

The outbreak of Salmonella poisoning in Pennsylvania can be traced back to the Quality Inn & Suites located in York, Pennsylvania. Still, three years later in April of 2016 the hotel was found to be in violation of 7 state health codes. None of the violations required a closure of the business, nor left the business out of compliance. In April of 2017, an annual inspection took place and the establishment was found to have violated an astonishing 26 statewide regulations, many of which risked severe contamination of food (Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture). During that year the business had seen a change in management. The businesses hygienic issues can be attributed to the lack of communication between the previous owner and the current one. Health regulations were not properly identified and emphasized during the transition, leading to an unacceptable level of hygiene.

The Quality Inn & Suites of York provides an example of why the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture should consider adding change of management inspections. A business undergoing a significant change in ownership must consider health a priority during the transition. The addition of change of management inspections would enforce the importance of health safety in the eyes of a business's ownership. The health of the people is in the hands of these safety inspectors. The inspections monitor a business's cleanliness and make sure the business adheres to crucial statewide mandates that ensure the health of the public. The Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture is supposed to maintain public health and ensure food safety, but now the agency is falling short.

The frequency of enteric outbreaks occurring in Pennsylvania is concerning. In a recent disease report published by the Pennsylvania Department of Health, from 2006 to 2013 an overall average case incidence of *Campylobacter* infections peaked at 49 cases per 100,000 people in Mifflin County. Overall, case reports come out to 15,017 reported cases from 2006 to 2013 (Cohrs 5). To put Pennsylvania's statewide health into perspective, The Center for Science in the Public Interest published a report reviewing and analyzing countrywide outbreak reports. All states were given a report card for their health level, in which they were graded based off the number of reported incidents and solved outbreaks. Pennsylvania received a "D" indicating a benchmark of 3 enteric outbreaks per million population (DeWaal 61). Compared to states like Texas, Arizona, and South Carolina which benchmarked less than 1 outbreak per two million population (DeWaal 11). Upon further investigation, it becomes clear why Pennsylvania suffers from so many enteric outbreaks.

Most outbreaks can be attributed to inadequate sanitation procedures following the handling of animal products. Take the *Campylobacter* bacteria for example; exposure to this bacterium occurs mainly following fecal contamination. Usually from "undercooked animal products or cross-contamination during food preparation." The most common form of *Campylobacter* transmission in Pennsylvania results from the human consumption of contaminated unpasteurized milk (Cohrs 6). Pennsylvania is one of 11 states where the sale of unpasteurized milk is legal (National Conference of State Legislatures). The legality of unpasteurized milk combined with the Pennsylvania Department of Health's lackadaisical safety inspection regulations has resulted in its concerningly high level of *Campylobacter* outbreaks.

Due to the legal status of raw milk within Pennsylvania, the number of statewide outbreaks attributed to the consumption of raw milk is the most in the country. According to the

Center for Disease Control and Prevention, Pennsylvania has had 17 outbreaks attributed to the consumption of raw milk over a 5-year period from 2007 to 2012. The next closest state was the state of Washington, which also legally allows the retail sale of unpasteurized milk.

The benefits of the public sale of raw milk are far outweighed by the consequences. The wellbeing of the public suffers greatly when unpasteurized milk is available for sale at retail stores. Milk from cows does not have a built-in safety measure to combat bacteria, hence the need for pasteurization. As the CDC states, “Raw milk, regardless of whether it is organic, can contain harmful germs.” The source of unpasteurized milk plays little role in ensuring its safety. The contamination of milk can occur at various stages of handling and processing. Safety standards applying to dairy product manufacturers must be reevaluated and improved by the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture.

Currently, dairy product manufacturers which have obtained a permit to sell raw milk must adhere to various safety standards set by the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture. One of these safety standards specified by the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture Bureau of Food Safety and Laboratory Services states that every 6 months, “a sample drawn from the bulk tank, [will be tested] for presence of the following pathogenic Bacteria including Salmonellae, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter*, and *E. Coli*”. The 6-month time frame in between lab tests can see vast changes within a raw milk distributors level of sanitation. As seen in the Quality Inn and Suites analyzed earlier, a great number of changes can happen to an establishment in between the listed safety inspections. To ensure raw milk manufacturers are consistently adhering to safety guidelines and reduce the time in between lab tests, the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture should transition from a 6-month time frame to a 3-

month time frame. More resources should be invested in the frequency of lab testing; if the time span is shortened, the chances of a contaminated product reaching the public is greatly reduced.

However, the sale of contaminated unpasteurized milk is only a small patch of grass within this unkempt lawn. The dangerous bugs reside in the emphasis of sanitation and cleanliness in businesses, or lack thereof.

I was able to witness the lackadaisical emphasis of sanitation and cleanliness in businesses during my time working in retail. I worked as a general floor staff employee at my local Harris Teeter grocery store. During my time as an employee there, I had countless interactions with fellow employees. Many of the store associates failed to follow any safety precautions mandated by store policy. Worker's ate on the job, failed to wash their hands and rarely used sanitizers and hand wipes when working with fresh foods. Management at the store failed to emphasize the importance of health procedures amongst employees. The store had put its focus on ensuring customer service rather than customer health because the former is what ensures a steady cash flow. Customers that are treated well tend to come back; so why not emphasize the importance of a friendly smile and disregard the cleanliness of fresh foods?

The question is as ridiculous as it sounds, but sanitation seems to come second to customer satisfaction (in the eyes of store management). To ensure the management of businesses understand the importance of public safety and health, the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture should mandate an 8-month inspection frame for all businesses related to the serving, production and handling of food. Reducing the time frame between safety inspections would prioritize sanitation and cleanliness over all other store policies. Establishments would be forced to frequently educate and remind their employees of the significance of healthy work

habits. Resulting in a reduced number of cross contamination cases and a lower chance of enteric outbreaks in Pennsylvania.

The Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture Inspections Database includes a disclaimer at the bottom of their webpage stating that “[any] inspection is a 'snapshot' of the day and time of the inspection. An inspection conducted on any given day may not be representative of the overall, long-term cleanliness of an establishment”. The use of the word “snapshot” couldn’t describe the lackadaisical nature of inspections any better. Allowing businesses to tidy up results in a misrepresentation of their actual cleanliness. At the current state, the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture has no way of conducting safety inspections that effectively evaluate levels of sanitation at businesses. Businesses are given a notice of inspection, and are given a considerable amount of time to adhere to mandated regulations. A business that should be out of compliance, and regularly violates statewide mandates goes unnoticed as the management of said establishment is given time to prepare for safety inspections. All outbreaks begin at businesses that are initially deemed compliant with state mandates and are considered cleanly and safe to the public. An inspector evaluation is nothing more than a single frame in the rolling tape of a business’s cleanliness.

The addition of randomized safety inspections for all businesses would be a costly endeavor. Sending inspectors out and publishing inspection reports at such a regular interval would be impossible. There would be no way to keep track of businesses due to sheer volume. However, instead of trying to account for all businesses, randomized safety inspections would only take place for those that have received hygiene complaints. The public could identify establishments that they believe are out of compliance, and the Pennsylvania Department of Agriculture could then perform a randomized safety inspection to evaluate safety concerns. This

would not only promote owners to stress the importance of their business's hygiene, but it would reassure the public that they have a voice to convey their health concerns. Reform has become a necessity, and the addition of randomized safety inspections could break the recurrent nature of health policy in Pennsylvania.

The opponents of agency reform claim that there is no need for improvements in safety inspections. They believe that the level of statewide hygiene is sufficient. Regarding the health inspections of businesses, there is no need for drastic evaluation and reform. They believe that the public is being provided with an ample safety net, and enteric outbreaks should not be of concern. However, the Pennsylvania Department of Health's Bureau of Epidemiology states otherwise; and the trend of foodborne illnesses in the state of Pennsylvania has been concerning to say the least.

Recent etiology (manner of causation of a disease) reports conclude that the prevention of foodborne outbreaks depends on the understanding and acknowledgement of state health reform. The subject of statewide health is one of importance and one of frequent change. Safety inspections must adapt to the needs of the public to ensure a consistent level of health. Appropriation of agency funds must be frequently changed to adhere to the enigmatic nature of public health and safety. The transmission of infectious agents can be reduced through the highlighting of safety procedures and their importance. Increasing the frequency of safety inspections would clearly state the essential nature of sanitation to business owners. The addition of randomized safety inspections would aid in the effectiveness of evaluation, and provide a more accurate depiction of a business's level of hygiene. Including change of management inspections would ensure that the transition between owners would maintain an acceptable level of hygiene. These reformations would be cost effective and simple to incorporate. It seems

illogical to not want to improve the health of the public. Opposing reformation that favors an increased level of public health seems unethical, as the lives of many people are in the hands of the inspectors and their evaluations. The maintenance of public health is a right of every state resident; to uphold that right, change must be expected, and an open mind is necessary to move forward.

The figurative lawn of public health is overgrown at the moment. However, the addition of a shortened 8-month inspection time frame, randomization of safety inspections and change of management safety inspections could ensure the well-being of the public. The handling of food determines the health of the public, the small changes in health safety policy could make all the difference when it comes to the long-lasting health of statewide communities. Everyone must eat, and we all want to be assured a safe meal. Why not invest in more time and effort to make such an assurance... after all, it's better to be safe than to be sorry.

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